

The History of the Archaeological Study and Inclusion of Uchtut Deposits in Science

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Abstract: In the primitive system, instead of the appropriating farm, which has reigned for millions of years, it has a new economic form - the emergence of a productive farm took place primarily in the southern regions of the globe, including in our Central Asian territory. This is due to the fact that scientists first show the compatibility of the weather of our generous land, and second they show the center of ancient Eastern culture relatively close to us.

Keywords: Uchtut deposit, archeological study, history, development.

The transition to a productive farm was called the “Neolithic revolution”, in which radical changes took place in the field of Economics. On the territory of Central Asia, the “Neolithic Revolution” began in the 1st century BC. in the 1st century BC. VI-IV dates from the Millennium. According to V.M.Masson, the internal laws of social progress and their interaction are the main factors, in which environmental science also has a special place[1]. The archaeologist Turgun Mirsoatov, adding to the opinions of the above scientists, shows that at the end of the Mesolithic and the beginning of the Neolithic, they switched to the use of quality lightning rods in public, putting an end to the use of raw materials that lost their quality as a result of the influence of the forces of nature from the ground level The following was the basis for such a conclusion of the Turgun Mirsoatov:

1. The transition from quality raw materials to the manufacture of labor weapons in turn led to an improvement in the quality of labor weapons made. Quality labor weapons, on the other hand, naturally provided an opportunity to accelerate progress in the farm.
2. Almost all over the world, the transition to the manufacture of Labor weapons from quality raw materials dates back to one era. Quality plates were flown from quality lightning rods. The blown plates were knife-shaped, reaching 35 cm in length. Archaeologically, the “Neolithic Revolution” dates from the same period. That is why the turgun Mirsoatov, making the main reasons for the occurrence of the “Neolithic Revolution”, indicates the extraction of quality raw materials from lightning deposits in many places of the globe and the transition from them to making quality labor weapons[3].

The result of the scientist's many years of excavations at the Uchtut monument suggests that the labor weapons of the tribes who lived in large and small Tuzkon settlements were mainly made from lightning bolts in the Uchtut mines. This was done in the laboratory of the Institute of Archeology of the USSR SA in Leningrad at the height of Large and Small Tuzkon U.Islamov confirmed the results of spectral analysis obtained from lightning weapons in the settlement found and from Uchtut deposits taken as raw materials[4].

In addition the discovery of camtic plates typical of the Caltaminor culture from each shaft in the Uchtut and the fact that the tribes of the Caltaminor culture in the Uchtut mines were in exchange with the Uchtut miners. The proof by T.Mirsoatov chronologically leads to the conclusion that the owners of the Caltaminor culture and the owners of the three mines are people of the same period[5]. T.Mirsoatov studied the Uchtut deposits in a comparative study with a very large number of Flint deposits in Europe, marked the starting in the BC. V millennium. It is worth noting that S.P.Tolstoy, A.V.Vinogradov, U. Islamovs expressed their opinion about the age of the Caltaminor culture, the Uchtut deposits were not yet known in archaeological science.

In addition to several hundreds of Neolithic settlements found in Uzbekistan, the Uchtut mines, which supplied raw materials for the making of labor weapons of these settlement tribes, were found in the fall of 1958 by X.Muhamedov, the head of a small group of Mohandarya expeditions led by Y.Ghulomov, and in 1959 A.P.Okladnikov shurfed here with the aim of identifying the monument. From 1961 to 1966 M.Kasimov conducted excavations at the Uchtut monument. M.Kasimov understood the Uchtut monument as a workshop (masterskoy) in his early research. Therefore, Uchtut divided the monument into squares and began to study it in the same way that it was used in the excavation of Paleolithic settlements. As a result, Neolithic shafts at 300 m² sites dug into the same squares were destroyed by demolition of their original, well-shaped appearance.

As a result of excavations in the Uchtut monument with a new method by the archaeologist T.Mirsoatov from 1967, it was found that the Uchtut monument is not a workshop, but a large object of the Neolithic era, providing raw materials for the manufacture of Labor weapons of the Caltaminor tribes around the Zarafshan Oasis, or rather lightning bolts[6]. That said, scientific research conducted by T.Mirsoatov on the Uchtut monument from 1967 to 1980 showed that the Uchtut monument, although the area is one, has 3 monuments that are chronologically sharply different, that is, divided into four periods and adjacent to each other. The total area of the monuments is 8,000 m². One of these 3 monuments is the workshop of the muste period, which includes 4% (320 m²) of the total area of the monument. The second monument is the object of obtaining raw materials in an open style, which includes 40% of the total area of the monument (3200 m²). The remaining 56% (4,480 m²) of the area is occupied by Neolithic deposits. Excavations were carried out by T.Mirsoatov at 1871 m² of an area of 8000 m² on all three monuments, and 38 shafts (mines) were found. A total of 111,852 artifacts were recovered from these, of which 2,178 were found to be labor weapons, more specifically weapons related to the extraction of lightning bolts from mines[7].

A comprehensive study of the archaeological finds in Uchtut showed that the extraction of flare from Uchtut to make labor weapons was different from all flare deposits on the globe and lasted for a very long time, more precisely from the muste period to the Neolithic. The period of obtaining lightning bolts from the Uchtut monument as raw materials is separated by T.Mirsoatov, leaning on evidential objects into four stages:

1. The use of Flint as raw materials in Phase 1 occurred during the Middle Paleolithic. In this, our ancestors used as raw materials for Labor weapons the fragments formed from the breakdown of lightning strikes that fell from the top of the mountains to the Voush mountain slopes of the Koratog as a result of the influence of nature. The reason for such a conclusion by T.Mirsoatov was the result of archaeological finds that came out of 7 horizons of the muste workshop, located on the upper part of the Uchtut monument. The VII-V horizons of the same workshop were of Middle Paleolithic age[8].

Stage 2 is formed by upper IV-I horizons from the last Paleolithic. If in the first stage our ancestors used raw materials endowed by nature, then in the second stage, that is, by the Upper Paleolithic, they were broken from lightning bolts in the form of a Xarsangtosh, which were located inside the mountain ridge with the help of otboynik (birch, which is convenient for beating and flying)and made weapons of labor from them.

In stage 3, humans openly plowed lightning stongs located within the Paleogene layer beneath the Neogene layer using labor weapons made from wood and reindeer branches. This stage is determined by the Mesolithic period. 456 M2 t of an area of 3200 M2 belonging to the Mesolithic period. Opened by T.Mirsoatov, a total of 5,404 stone objects were found, of which 341 (6.31%) were weapons of labor, determined by the method of experiment and trassology.

Stage 4 is the Neolithic shafts of the Uchtut monument, of which 38 was opened as a result of the use of a new method by T.Mirsoatov. A total of 103,393 artifacts were recovered from these mines, of which a total of 3.15% were found to be weapons of labor. The rest were waste. The shapes of the 38 opened shafts were mostly well-shaped, ranging from 2m to 7m 20cm. Width ranges from 1 m to 2m 65cm. They are almost all relatively wide on top at the base and most are extended at the expense of special galleries and podboys at the base. Individual shafts are joined to the base sections by a corridor.

Of particular note, thirty-two chemically prism-shaped plates were found in the Uchtut deposits, which were all characteristic of the Caltaminor culture. Along with many other evidential objects, it is the discovery of 32 of the Uchtut shafts of plates typical of this Caltaminor culture that T.Mirsoatov was plowed by the owners of the Uchtut shafts of the Caltaminor culture, even later special groups separated from them, which led to the conclusion that these groups were engaged only in the extraction of lightning rods, and they lived at the expense of exchange. The correctness of such a conclusion was noted by the employee of the Institute of Archaeology of the Leningrad branch of the USSR science it was confirmed by the result of spectral analysis conducted by V.A.Golibin in the laboratory. As a result, it was determined where the lightning bolts from the Uchtut shafts were taken, that is, its "trade" paths. The basis for such a conclusion is that samples of labor weapons made of lightning rods were taken from each of the 35 sites of the Caltaminor culture found by U.Islamov, which, when compared with the composition of the flint in the Uchtut, as shown above, found them to be the same in composition.

So, as a raw material for making labor weapons, the monuments belonging to the Caltaminor culture mainly used lightning bolts from the Uchtut mines. Until the emergence of conclusions based on such evidential objects, there were different opinions in archaeological science. B.A.Litvinsky wrote that "there should be underground lightning deposits in Central Asia, but so far it is not clear to us". M.E.Masson has stated that there are opinions that Neolithic people in the Central Asian region brought and used lightning bolts from other places, more Urals, as they are not in Central Asia, making them agree that the Urals show that the lightning bolts are similar in appearance to the flint jeans of labor weapons on Central Asian monuments. "But, says M.E. Masson there must have been underground lightning deposits in – Central Asia, but they have not yet been found"[9].

The correctness of these conclusions of M.E.Masson was fully confirmed by the fact that over the years, the discovery by T.Mirsoatov of not one to 40 lightning mines, even determining who dug them and where they were taken, and what kind of Labor weapons were made. The most important thing was to prove that our ancestors had their own reserves of raw materials, showing that even in the Stone Age they did not need others. In order to accurately mark the Uchtut deposits, it is of great importance to find the right research style to have the lightness when digging them. The study of the monument was carried out in two styles: one was in 1961-1967 workshop by M. Kasimov (masterskoy)[10], the latter in 1967-1985 were mine (mining) styles used by T.Mirsoatov. Uchtut deposits are not in standard form, and often differ from each other (both in depth and in size). Note that Uchtut shafts are divided into the following groups:

- 1) borehole;
- 2) single chamber;
- 3) multi-chamber, stairs.

Many years of research, experimentation, and trassological techniques in the Uchtut mine and muste-era workshop have shown that the mine is the main deposits in the arms production of ancient humans in and around the Zarafshan Oasis. It is clear that the excavations were carried out in a nonegular, moment-by-moment manner. Ancient miners carried out excavations in the summer season. Because it was difficult to dig on days of bad rainy weather. The ancient miners lived near the flint mines and were engaged only in the excavation of it. The horns of Bukhara reindeer found in the mines indicate that only one tribe was engaged in mining operations here[11]. Study of the Uchtut monument allowed T.Mirsoatov to tell a number of scientific innovations:

1. The investigation of the Uchtut monument revealed 4 stages of lightning mining involving the period from Muste to Neolithic.
2. At each excavation stage of lightning, methods of its excavation were identified, and the dynamics of the development of weapons assisting in the mining work was studied.
3. In the Central Asian two river range area, the presence of commodity exchange, the first shoots of the division of labor in the Mesolithic end and Neolithic heads was studied.
4. A “trade route” has been identified that delivers Uchtut lightning bolts to customers.
5. Questions about the periodization, chronology and cultural objects of the monuments under study were covered.
6. The tasks of the Central Asian two-river range according to the type of farm of the Mesolithic and Neolithic labor weapons were determined.
7. The solution to the perceived problems formed (relatively new)visions of the ancient history of Central Asia. This is how its scientific significance is expressed. So, while most of the Flint deposits known to us so far on Earth date only from the Neolithic period, it turned out that the use of Flint in the Uchtut monument dates back to the Middle Paleolithic. Evidence of this can be shown by the Middle Paleolithic workshop flanked by the Uchtut mines, and the tools of labor and rapidaceous grooves, necluses from the same period found from it.

In conclusion to the above, it is worth noting that the history of the making of labor weapons from lightning weapons of our ancestors on the Koratogs of the current Navoi region began in the Middle Paleolithic and continued continuously throughout the Neolithic. T. Mirsoatov scientifically proved that our ancestors had their own reserves of raw materials from time immemorial, that raw materials were not imported from the Urals. The history of the perfect study and inclusion of Uchtut deposits in science has been covered by the scientist's series of articles, two scientific monographs and scientific works inherited by us.

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